

Reactive and proactive prevention of adolescent pregnancy in the community

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Abstract

Adolescence is a well-defined stage of the human life cycle that lies between childhood and adulthood. Teenage pregnancy becomes a complex public health problem. In the development of adolescent pregnancy, the different risk factors must be identified. It is necessary to implement biopsychosocial strategies for the reactive and proactive prevention of adolescent pregnancy in the community.

Keywords: Teen; Pregnancy; Community; Prevention

1. Introduction

Adolescence is a well-defined stage of the human life cycle that lies between childhood and adulthood; it is characterized by profound physical, sexual, psychological and social changes. ^(1, 2) Among the most relevant problems that occur in adolescence, we can mention pregnancy. Pregnancy, at increasingly early ages, is emerging as a global social and public health problem. ⁽³⁾ One of the predisposing factors for adolescent pregnancy is the early onset of sexual life, the Latin American and Caribbean region constitutes an area where it is estimated that approximately 22% of girls begin their sexual life before reaching the age of fifteen. ⁽⁴⁾

Teenage pregnancies represent one of the main risks of preterm delivery, low birth weight, hypertensive disease of pregnancy, maternal and fetal deaths, spontaneous abortion, and genital hemorrhage, urinary or vaginal infections, among others. ⁽⁵⁾ When pregnancy occurs in a socioeconomically disadvantaged adolescent, the probability of death, fetal, perinatal and maternal disability increases by up to 50%. ⁽⁶⁾

2. Dear Editor

The incidence of adolescent pregnancy varies, depending on the region and the degree of development of the country studied. ^(7, 8, 9) Adolescent pregnancy becomes a complex public health problem due to its sociocultural configuration in each context in which the adolescent develops his life, where economic and cultural aspects, social and community networks influence the ways of understanding and acting of the adolescent before, during and after pregnancy. It is a priority as health professionals to educate to contribute to reducing the number of adolescent pregnancies.

When interacting with these young pregnant women, a deficient pregnancy prevention is denoted in their proactive vision: the identification of those areas, services, processes, in which it is foreseeable that security incidents occur, in

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order to modify the aspects that can cause them, reactive prevention prevails in them: the identification of incidents with or without damage to the patient's condition, after their occurrence. ⁽¹⁰⁾

Adolescent pregnancy care must be deployed with the greatest subtlety and prudence. It is extremely important to pay attention to ethical aspects, without intrusiveness to the culture and idiosyncrasies of the family and of pregnant adolescents. To achieve better effects in the health strategies carried out, it will always be necessary to reconcile or agree on orientations or criteria involved in the actions and activities, without impositions or directive advice.

In the development of adolescent pregnancy, the different risk factors must be identified, of an individual, social and family order, so that its prevention should encourage the participation of the adolescent, the school, the family, the community in general, with development of comprehensive sexuality education. The conception of health as a state of physical, mental and social well-being, functioning capacity, quality of life and as dignified and safe conditions for life, are acquisitions in the social representation of health. ⁽¹¹⁾

It is necessary to implement biopsychosocial strategies for the reactive and proactive prevention of adolescent pregnancy in the community. Direct these actions towards the functioning and full benefit of life. Achieve a favorable development of adolescence, incorporated into educational activities, with a coherent and systemic nature, which are part of the work system of the health sector and the community in general.

3. Conclusion

Biological, psychological and social factors are present in the individual, family, community and society when interacting with the health-disease process, which offers strategic space and real possibility for the development of actions and activities that contribute to reactive and proactive prevention. of adolescent pregnancy in the community.

Compliance with ethical standards

Author's contribution

González Pérez RB. and Mirabal Requena JC.: Conception or design of the work. Data collection. Data analysis and interpretation. Drafting the article. Final approval of the version to be published.

Rodríguez Mateo M. and Alvarez Escobar B.: Data analysis and interpretation. Critical revision of the article. Final approval of the version to be published

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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